

Study of the Grignard Reaction on 3,4-Diaryl Coumarins[†]

SUPRABHAT RAY, MANJU KUMARI, P. L. KOLE, P. K. GROVER** and NITYA ANAND*

Medicinal Chemistry Division, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow-226 001

The nature of the product formed in the reaction of MeMgI on 3,4-diaryl coumarins is greatly affected by the substituents present on the coumarin ring and presumably depends on the molecular geometry of the coumarin and the induced effect on the polarisability of its carbonyl group. The products formed in each case have been identified and possible mechanism of formation has been proposed.

FOR a projected synthesis of 2,2-disubstituted-3,4-diaryl chromenes and related compounds, Grignard reaction on coumarins seemed a very attractive route. During this study some interesting observations were made regarding the structure of the coumarin molecules and the Grignard reaction products. The influence of electronic and steric factors on the reactivity of the coumarin carbonyl, its accessibility to the attacking reagent and the formation of the ultimate product is reported in this communication.

The scope of Grignard reaction on coumarins¹ for the synthesis of natural products² and in various other synthetic organic reactions has been extensively investigated. It has been reported that the reaction leads to 1,2-, 1,4-addition products³ and may result in dimerisation⁴ depending upon the substituents on the coumarin ring, type of the Grignard reagent and the reaction conditions used. However, 3,4-diaryl coumarins, due to steric reasons, undergo 1,2-addition only⁴. With Grignard reagent of a lower alkyl halide the addition of the first mole of the reagent on 3,4-diaryl coumarins (Fig. 1) takes place on to the coumarin carbonyl which may give rise to α , β -unsaturated ketone (III). In the presence of an excess of the Grignard reagent, further attack on II or III leads to *gem*-dialkyl carbinol (IV) that may cyclise, under acidic conditions to 2,2-dialkyl-3,4-diarylchromenes (V).

Fig. 1

To study the effect of the substituents and the impact of the molecular geometry on the outcome of the Grignard reaction, various 3,4-diaryl coumarins, corresponding 5,6-benzocoumarins and phenanthro(9,10-c) coumarins were reacted with MeMgI under comparable conditions. The reaction of 3,4-diphenyl-6-methyl coumarin (VI) with MeMgI in ether-THF mixture, refluxing for 5 hr and decomposing with NH_4Cl and trace of acid, gave 2-methyl-3,4-diphenyl-4-(2-hydroxy-5-methyl)phenyl-but-3-en-2-ol (VII) in 65% yield, m.p. 157° ; IR: $\nu(\text{KBr})$ 3180 and 3450 cm^{-1} (OH); on mild acid treatment VII cyclised to 2,2,6-trimethyl-3,4-diphenyl- Δ^8 -chromene (VIII); m.p. 105° ; IR: $\nu(\text{KBr})$ 1380, 1365 cm^{-1} ($-\text{CMe}_2$, NMR: 88 (s, 6H, $-\text{CMe}_2$), 128 Hz (s, 3H, Ar. CH_3). This butenol (VII), however, appeared to be unstable and on keeping (several days), it gradually decomposed and transformed into mainly 2,3-diphenyl-5-methylbenzofuran (IX), identical in all respects with an authentic sample prepared through an unambiguous route⁵. This transformation process could be accelerated by refluxing a benzene solution of VII in the presence of a catalytic amount of benzoyl peroxide. Similar result could be obtained by passing O_2 through a benzene solution of VII for 5 hr. The rate of reaction was found to be unaffected in the absence of light. From the above reaction mixture, two other products which were isolated and characterized on the basis of their physical data and comparison with authentic samples were 2-(0-benzoyl)-5-methylbenzophenone (X) and 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone⁶ (XI). However, phenol acetate (XII) was found to be completely inert towards this transformation which indicated the involvement of the lone pair of electrons on the phenolic OH of VII in this transformation.

Based on the above observations, the transformation of VII to IX may be presumed to be taking place through a free radical pathway (Fig. 2). The free radical generated on C-3 of VII either led to the formation of IX or was attacked by an oxygen diradical giving 1,2-oxetane compound (XIII). The cleavage of the oxetane ring was initiated by the lone pair of electrons of the dihydrobenzofuran (XIII) and led to the benzoyl ester X which subsequently hydrolysed to the benzophenone (XI).

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** Associate Director of Research, Sarabhai Research Centre, Wadi Wadi, Baroda-390 007.

Fig. 2

However, when I was allowed to react with a limited quantity of MeMgI (1.2 moles) by reverse addition technique; the reaction mixture decomposed with HCl; the product extracted with ether, concentrated and treated with MeOH, a complicated mixture of products was obtained. This mixture on column chromatography on basic alumina using increasing proportion of benzene in hexane as eluant gave chromene (VIII), partly unreacted coumarin (I) and 10% yield of 2-methoxy-2,6-dimethyl-3,4-diphenylchromene (XIV) as a light orange coloured solid, m.p. 124°; NMR: 205 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 130 (s, 3H, Ar.CH₃), 91 (s, 3H, C-CH₃) and 418 Hz (m, 14H, ArH). The formation of XIV arising out of mono addition of MeMgI in such a poor yield indicated the tremendous facile diaddition leading to the formation of VIII. The presence of a hydroxyl group at *para* position in the 4-phenyl residue or at 7-position of the coumarin nucleus helped in the release of *t*-OH formed in Grignard reaction and led to the formation of 2,2-dimethylchromenes directly.

Introduction of an additional benzene ring at 5,6-position of the coumarin, did not noticeably alter the rate of addition of MeMgI but had a marked influence on the subsequent course of reaction. The reaction of 5,6-benzocoumarins (XV) with MeMgI⁷ (Fig. 3) gave dimethyl carbinols (XVI) even in the presence of an electron donating group at *para*-position of the 4-phenyl residue, which might indicate that, in this case, the 4-phenyl ring was thrown out of plane of the butene double bond. Treatment of the carbinol (XVI) under acidic condition gave 1,1-dimethyl-2,3-diphenyl phenalene (XIX) instead of 2,2-dimethyl-3,4-diphenyl-5,6-benzochromenes (XVII). The *peri*-position of naphthalene thus preferentially attacked the

carbonium ion (XVIII) forming the phenalenes (XIX). Cyclisation to the chromenes (XVII) could be achieved by passing a benzene solution of XVI through a column of silica gel. A rearrangement of chromenes (XVII) to phenalenes (XIX) was observed under acidic conditions.

R = H, OH or OCH₃

Fig. 3

Fusion of the phenyl rings at 3 and 4-positions of coumarin in the form of phenanthro(9,10-c)coumarins⁸, had a pronounced effect on the reactivity of the coumarin carbonyl in Grignard reactions (Fig. 4).

R = H or CH₃

Fig. 4

Thus, treatment of XX (R=H) with MeMgI (5 mol) gave 9-(2-hydroxy)phenyl-10-acetylphenanthrene (XXI) (R=H) as the major product (60%), m.p. 205°; IR: ν (KBr) 1675 (CO), 3400 cm⁻¹ (OH); NMR: 137 Hz (s, 3H, COCH₃) and XX (R=CH₃) gave XXI (R=CH₃), m.p. 138°, (IR: ν (KBr) 1675 (CO), 3400 cm⁻¹ (OH), NMR: 137 (s, 3H, COCH₃) 135 Hz (s, 3H, Ar.CH₃). This reluctance of the carbonyl to undergo further addition of MeMgI appeared to be steric controlled which was supported by the observation⁸ that whereas 3,4-diphenylcoumarins on photolysis gave phenanthro(9,10-c)coumarins with reasonable ease, the

corresponding 2,2-dimethyl-chromenes were recovered unchanged.

Thus, it may be concluded that in the Grignard reaction with 3,4-diarylcoumarins the rate and degree of attack of the Grignard reagent appeared to be steric controlled and the subsequent step leading to the isolation of the final product was greatly influenced by electronic factors and reaction conditions.

All the compounds reported gave the expected elemental analysis. The IR spectra were taken on infracord 337 and NMR spectra were recorded on varian A-60D spectrometer using CDCl_3 as solvent and SiMe_4 as internal standard.

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